

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS & PAPERS

- Cocodia, E. A.** (2020). Anxiety. In *Client Issues in Counselling*. Queensland: University of Southern Queensland Press (under contract)
- Onslow-MacArthur, L. & **Cocodia E. A.** (2020): Mental health and Wellbeing: The Rogerian Approach (under review)
Walter, J., & **Cocodia E. A.** (2019). Volunteer counselling and counsellor burnout. *Psychological Sciences*, (accepted manuscript)
- Carbone, S. & **Cocodia E. A.** (2019). Bullying and the effects on mental health. *Education Quarterly Review*, 2 (2), 386-394.
- Cocodia, E. A.** (2019). eSafety and mental health of young people: Current issues. *Counselling Australia Journal*, 20 (3).
- Cocodia, E.A.** (2018). Mental health and wellbeing: focus on indigenous communities. Encyclopaedia of Behavioural Sciences and Psychology. Online: <https://encyclopedia.pub/9>
- Cocodia, E.A.** (2018). Reflecting on Rogers' person-centred therapy and Clinbell's approach. Encyclopaedia of Behavioural Sciences and Psychology. Online: <https://encyclopedia.pub/>
- Dedeigbo O. & **Cocodia E. A.** (2017). Domestic violence in Australia's CALD communities. *Asia Pacific Journal of Advanced Social Studies*, 3(1), 2205-6603.
- Dedeigbo O. & **Cocodia E. A.** (2016). Discourse analysis on the efficacy fo therapeutic approaches for victims of domestic violence associated with Australia's CALD communities. *International Journal of Applied Science Research*, 2(9), 50-54
- Athota, S., Kearney S. & **Cocodia, E.A.** (2015). How self-transcendence via individualised moral foundations predict emotional and social enhancement. *Journal of Beliefs & Values: Studies in Religion & Education*, 36(3) 297-307.
- Cocodia, E. A.** (2015). Assessing for rising visuospatial ability of school leavers. *International Journal of Psychological Studies*, 7 (2), 113-120.
- Cocodia E. A.** (2014). Cultural perceptions of human intelligence. *Journal of Intelligence*, 12(4), 180-196.
- Cocodia E. A.** (2014). Developing a career counselling and development program for medical sciences students: Reflecting "in" and "on" practice. *Higher Education Studies*, 4(2), 24-30.
- Cocodia, E. A.** (2014). Are Kids Getting Smarter? Perceptions of Abilities. *Psychology*, 15, 1469-1476.
- Cocodia, E. A.** (2013). On happiness in counselling practice. *Counselling Australia Journal*, December, 2013.
- Cocodia, E. A.** (2013). Reflective frameworks and the assessment of ethical issues. *Journal of the Counsellors and Psychotherapists Association (CAPA) Quarterly*, Issue 4, November 2013.
- Cocodia, E. A.** (2013). Modality: On person-centered therapy. *Journal of the Counsellors and Psychotherapists Association (CAPA) Quarterly*, Issue 3, August 2013.
- Nguyen, A., Bert, O. P, Lau, G., Allen, K. A., & Smith, J., & **Cocodia, E.**, (2009). What does a poor prognosis in breast cancer mean for me? A review of the clinical findings. *International Cancer Research* 34, 91-98.
- Smith, B., Elias, D., Lu, C, Hussien, A., **Cocodia, E.**, & Albert, W. A. (2008). Stages of drug-based chemotherapy: Examining an individualised approach. *Journal of Clinical Cancer Research* 14,1, 115-121.
- Cocodia, E.A.** (2005). Psychological aspects of student learning processes: a cross-cultural analysis. *Journal of International Education & Human Development* 71 ,523-530.
- Cocodia, E. A.**, Kim, J., Shin, H., Kim, J., Ee, J., Wee, M.S., & Howard, R.W. (2003). Evidence that rising population intelligence is impacting in formal education setting. *Journal of Personality and Individual Differences* 35, 797-810.

Adeyemi, O., Williams, K. O., & **Cocodia, E. A.** (1999). From research to practice: Analysis of selected education programs in regional settings. *African Journal of Education Studies* 51, 214-219.

Adeyemi, O., Williams, K. O., Aideyan, C., Ayeni, F.A., **Cocodia, E. A.** (2000). An assessment of nomadic training in the current curriculum. In K. O. Williams, & R. A. Simeon (Eds.), *Assessment of the national training framework for teacher education in state institutions* (pp.154-162). Lagos: Lagos Press.

Braimoh, J., Oyeniyi, B. **Cocodia, E. A.** Offiong, E. & Temowo, O. L. (2001). Evaluating the link between nominated electives and subsequent performance in selected science subjects across the region. In B. Oyeniyi & E. S. Adeniyi (Eds.), *Providing guidance for students in The West African Examination Council Social Science subjects* (pp. 49-56). Lagos: PPL Academic Publishers.

Dedeigbo, O. & **Cocodia, E. A.** (2016). Domestic violence in Australia's CALD communities. In conference proceedings of the Asia Pacific Conference of Advance Research, July 29-30, Melbourne, Australia.

Dedeigbo, O. & **Cocodia, E. A.** (2016). A discourse analysis: Efficacy of therapeutic approaches when working with victims of domestic violence in Australia's CALD communities. In conference proceedings of the International Conference of Social Science and Economics, July 4-5, Sydney, Australia.

Cocodia, E. A. (2014). What is your (dis)Ability? Inclusive education tin higher education. In conference proceedings of the Disability in Education Studies Conference, July 25-27, Victoria University, Melbourne, Australia.

Cocodia, E. A. (2013). Reflective practice within a community of practice: an undergraduate cohort experience. In conference proceedings of SCAPE Annual Conference, 27-28 April, 2013, University of Adelaide, South Australia.

Cocodia, E. A. (2012). Reflective practice in assessment & intervention: Gender perspectives in a cultural context. In conference proceedings of the Australian Women's and Gender Studies Biannual Conference, 21-23 November 2012, University of NSW, Sydney Australia.

Cocodia, E.A. (2011). Reflecting on our counselling practice. Invited paper: Counsellors in Community Settings, 3-5 June 2011, Balgowlah, NSW.

Tan, J. L., Thomson, K., **Cocodia, E.A.**, & Kim. C. (2010). Breast cancer survivors and well-being: The road to recovery. Paper presented at the Garvan Institute of Medical Research Seminar Series, February 4-5, Darlinghurst, NSW.

Cocodia, E.A. (2009). School counselling in developing economies. In conference proceedings of the 3rd International Education Conference, November 20-21, Ikeja, Lagos.

Wong, A., Mullings, F., Johnson, P. A., & **Cocodia, E.A.** (2008). Caring for cancer patients with a diagnosis of early detected ovarian cancer. Paper presented at the International Association of Advances in Medical Sciences Meeting, 10-13 March 2008, London, UK.

Cocodia, E.A. (2008). International education and student success: Developing a framework for the global educator. In conference proceedings of the Eastern Institute of Technology Teaching and Learning Conference, 1-3 October 2008, Hawkes Bay, New Zealand.

Cocodia, E.A. (2007). Educational challenges of Sudanese migrants in Greater Western Sydney. Paper presented at the University of Western Sydney URG Meeting, 20 September 2007, Bankstown, New South Wales.

Cocodia, E.A. (2006). Accessing help for carers in rural Nova Scotia. Paper presented at the Council for Rural Women Conference, April 18-19, NS, Canada

Cocodia, E.A. (2005). Education and technological advancement in rural Nova Scotia. Paper presented at the Roundtable for Women, December 12-14, Halifax, Canada

Cocodia, E.A. (2005). Developing a psychological framework for educators: rising general intelligence and visuospatial abilities. In conference proceedings of the British Psychological Society's Psychology of Education Section Annual Conference, 5-7 November 2004 (p.121-122). Glasgow, UK.

Cocodia, E.A. (2003). Teacher perceptions and examinations performance. In conference proceedings of the Hawaii International Conference on Social Sciences, June 12 - 15, 2003, Honolulu, Hawaii, USA.

Cocodia, E.A. (2002). When do teachers fail students? Teaching and learning in a range of settings. In conference proceedings of the Education Technology Conference, Jan 6 - 8, 2002, Nevada, USA.

Sesan, B., Olayemi, O. T., & **Cocodia, E.A.** (2000). Standards of teaching social science in Isolo local government area schools. Paper presented at The 15th Association of Social Science Teachers Conference, April 16-19, Marina, Lagos.